

Effect of aeration on the suitability of secondary treated sewage by UASB reactor followed by algal pond for tertiary treatment with aquaculture

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received– 21 June, 2017

Revised– 26 October, 2017

Accepted– 20 November, 2017

Available– 30 December, 2017
(online)

Keywords:

UASB

Secondary effluent

Algal biomass

Aquaculture

Tilapia

Water quality

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ABSTRACT

The present research deals with the application of Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (UASB) treated secondary effluent in aquaculture purpose for tertiary treatment. The UASB effluent followed by algal pond was used as nutrient enriched water resource for aquaculture practices using tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) under different periods of aeration – 24 h, 12 h (at day), 12 h (at night) and no aeration. Fish growth influencing physico-chemical qualities of water and fish growth were observed during the period of experimentation. The results obtained from experiment showed that the specific growth rate (SGR, 1.3875%) of fishes in 12 h (at night) aeration was higher compared to other aeration conditions with favourable physico-chemical qualities of water. Therefore, it can be concluded that UASB treated secondary effluent driven algal and tilapia production is a potential ecotechnological approach for treating the wastewater as well as producing fish proteins. Furthermore, cost of fish byproducts could be used in sewage treatment.

1. Introduction

Water pollution is become a foremost problem throughout the world. Massive amount of water is getting polluted daily due to various anthropogenic activities, which is a severe problem in respect to environmental pollution (Kundu et al. 2016). Rivers and lakes acts as a precious resources for our livelihood to live. A huge amount of chemical or xenobiotic contaminants, from different sources, has become threat to the surface water resources of the world. Lack of fresh water resources is a tremendous problem in today's world. Water is most likely the only natural resource to finger all aspects of human civilization from agricultural and industrial progress to the cultural ethics in society.

Therefore, use of wastewater for pisciculture facilitates the purification system through natural means. Thus, it may contribute towards nutritional security through the use of waste water in aquaculture (Jana 1998). In India, utilization of

sewage water, a traditional knowledge, for the production of fish is benign for human consumption and ensure the supply throughout the year (Dasgupta et al. 2008; Kumar et al. 2015). Mechanization of system gives better output as well as serves as a cost recovery option to minimize or recover operational investments, and is mostly eco-friendly (Kumar and Kumar 2017). From several decades, aquaculture through traditional knowledge is followed and in State of West Bengal, India, world largest sewage-fed pisciculture system has been practiced (Kumar and Asolekar 2014).

Fishes depend on water temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide, alkalinity and some other salts for growth and development (Nikolosky 1963). Any change in these parameters may affect the growth, development, maturity of fish and even may causes death of the fish (Jhingram 1985; Mondal et al. 2015).

The water quality may also affect the quality of aquaculture products and its suitability for human

consumption. Zweig et al. 1999 noted that even if culture species are able to grow and thrive in a given source of water, low levels of pollutants may cause the aquaculture products to be contaminated or have off-flavor. Adeniji and Ovie (1982) observed that temperature, turbidity, suspended solids, dissolved oxygen concentration are among other primary factors that determine the quality of a water body. However, dissolved oxygen is the utmost important and critical parameter which requires continuous monitoring because in the aerobic metabolism of the fish, dissolved oxygen is required (Timmons et al. 2001). Requirement of oxygen vary along with the characteristics of waste water and design of aquaculture. Requirement of oxygen may vary with various water conditions and system to system. Thus, requirement of dissolved oxygen in the aquaculture system leads to focus in the utilization of Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (UASB) treated secondary effluent in aquaculture purpose for tertiary treatment. The present work deals with the application of Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (UASB) treated secondary effluent in aquaculture purpose for tertiary treatment using tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) under different periods of aeration – 24 h, 12 h (at day), 12 h (at night) and no aeration.

2. Materials and methods

The study is carried out by providing different conditions as: With 24 h aeration in Aquarium-1; With 12 h day time aeration in Aquarium-2; With 12 hrs night time aeration in Aquarium-3 and without aeration in Aquarium-4. The experimental set up (Fig. 1) is set in Aquacultural Engineering Workshop to fulfill the study criteria and for proper observation. Tilapia were used in this experiment due to many advantages such as good growth rate, wide range of tolerance towards environmental conditions (such as DO, salinity, temperature, etc), highly resistivity towards stress and disease including acceptance of artificial feed.

2.1. Water quality monitoring

Water quality is usually defined as the suitability of water for survival and growth of fishes and it is normally governed by few variables (Boyd 1978). Most of these properties can be measured with appreciable degree of accuracy and the data can be used for productivity management of the pond. Evaluation of water quality was carried out on each 5 days cycle by collecting the samples.

2.1.1. Water quality of algal pond water

Wastewater was collected from the algal pond of UASB reactor situated in the IIT, Kharagpur campus. Characterization of the wastewater was carried out by following the standard technique APHA, 1998. Sewage after treatment through the UASB reactor was treated further in algal pond. The treated secondary effluent water from UASB reactor passed to algal pond where Tilapia fishes are grown.

2.1.2. pH

The pH was measured using digital pH meter with sensitivity of 0.01 and having temperature correction facility. The pH was measured by placing electrode in the sample. The instrument was calibrated periodically with standard buffer solutions.

2.1.3. Dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature

The Dissolved oxygen was measured with YSI (MODEL 55) DO meter. This DO meter is consists of a probe comprising of two electrodes both bathed in potassium chloride and separated from the water by means of a membrane. One electrode measure DO and another one temperature. Both the parameters were measured on daily basis. Water temperature was measured using temperature probe which is available on YSI (MODEL 55) DO meter.

Fig. 1 Experimental set up for study of fish growth in secondary treated effluent under controlled condition

2.1.4. Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)

It is an important regulatory parameter used to indicate organic strength of the wastewater. For BOD measurement, diluted sample was kept in the incubator for three days. The change in DO concentration in the water sample was measured over the three days incubation period at 20°C. Then BOD value was calculated by following formula:

$$\text{BOD} = \frac{(D_1 - D_2) - (B_1 - B_2)f}{P}$$

Where,

D_1 = DO on first day

B_1 = DO of blank on first day

D_2 = DO on third day

B_2 = DO of blank on third day

f = Seed volume ratio

P = Wastewater decimal fraction

The BOD was measured on every four days cycle.

2.1.5. Chemical oxygen demand (COD)

COD of the anodic chamber influent and effluent were measured in each 3 days (d) cycle by closed reflux colorimetric method as mentioned in Standard Methods for Treatment of Water and wastewater (APHA 1998). Refluxing was done for 2 h in capped hatch tubes with potassium dichromate and H_2SO_4 (COD reagent) in a hatch digester, and the oxygen consumed was measured against standard at 600 nm with a spectrophotometer (Model: UV 1700 Spectrometer, Shimadzu).

2.1.6. Most probable number (MPN)

The MPN is a method of estimating the total coliform in water. It is more practical to examine water for indication of bacteriological contamination. For each sample tested, reagent amounts were added as 5*10 mL to 10 mL double strength Lactose Broth (LB), 5*1 mL to 5 bottles single strength LB, 5*0.1 mL to 5 bottles single strength LB, and Durham tubes are completely filled. The incubation temperature is fixed at 37°C and due to acid production, yellow coloration generates, and gas trapped in Durham tube. Those tubes that produce acid and gas are scored positive. By

varying sample size and number, it is possible to build up a statistical picture as to the numbers present. These are represented in the McCray tables. The procedure followed for this test is as described by APHA (1998).

2.1.7. Estimation of ammonia nitrogen ($\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$)

The ammonia nitrogen was measured using Spectrometer (Model: UV 1700 Spectrometer, Shimadzu). 10 mL of filtered water sample was taken into which 3 mL of Nessler's reagent was added. The solution was mixed thoroughly and kept for 15 minutes. Then ammonia nitrogen was measured in every 5 days interval.

2.1.8. Turbidity

Turbidity was measured using secchi disc method. Initially algal pond water was checked for enrichment in organic suspended matter.

2.1.9. Measurement of weight of fish

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The growth was calculated on the basis of weight gain by fish on each 15 d intervals. The growth is also measured in terms of length of fish. The fish size is also measured on every 15 d cycle. Five numbers of fishes were released to the aquarium. The standard and total size was measured. The average weight of fishes was measured in every 10 d interval.

SGR (specific growth rate) was calculated to evaluate the fish growth and health.

$$\text{SGR} = 100 \times \frac{\ln\left(\frac{\text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}}\right)}{\text{Culture periods (days)}}$$

2.1.10. Algal dry weight estimation

Dry Cell Weight (DCW) was estimated as per the protocol of Rai et al. (1991). A noted quantity of microalgae culture was centrifuged for 10 min at 5000 rpm, after which the harvested biomass was dried at 60°C till a constant weight was reached. The biomass concentration was expressed as g/L.

Table 1 Characteristics of algal pond water

Parameter	Value
Temperature	22°C ± 7.89
pH	8.9 to 9.6
COD	45 ± 5.66 mg/L
BOD	15 ± 5.89 mg/L
TSS	85 ± 7.65 mg/L
VSS	70 ± 6.89 mg/L
NH_3	4 ± 0.86 mg/L
PO_4	0.2-0.3 mg/L
Alkalinity	150 ± 10.33 mg/L
DO	4 ± 2.2 mg/L

3. Results and discussion

The results obtained during characterization of raw sewage, laboratory experiments on treatment of wastewater using UASB reactor and algal pond have been discussed in this section. The sewage treated in this method can be further used for aquaculture. The performance of sewage-fed aquaculture has been reported in terms of waste nutrients removal as well as fish growth.

3.1. Characteristics of raw sewage

For characterization of the sewage obtained from IIT Kharagpur campus, samples were collected for various measuring various water quality parameters such as pH, DO, COD, BOD, SS, Ammonia, Phosphate and MPN. Table 1 represents the characteristics of sewage collected from the algal pond.

3.2. Characteristics of the water used as culture medium

The parameters were maintained as required for successful aquaculture. The parameters such as DO, pH, Temperature were mainly maintained. The alternate dark and light condition was provided to algae for proper growth. The pH of aquarium pond water was measured on every 4 days interval. The pH data for Aquarium 1, 2, 3 and 4 was initially 9.6. After 15 days of the experiment, the pH decreased to 9. After 20 days, the pH values were within the range of 6.5 - 8.9 and it was maintained during the whole experiment. The pH values of all aquariums decreases and it was around 8.5, this was suitable for aquaculture practices. The turbidity of algal pond water was around 22 - 25 cm and due to high turbidity range, pH value also decreases. The DO

of sewage water in every aquarium was measured on every alternate day. The DO variation in aquarium with 24 h aeration, 12 h day time aeration, 12 h night time aeration and in absence of aeration. The DO data varies according to aeration quantity. The aquaria were controlled with aeration more than 5 mg/L. The DO level was below 100% saturation level but controlled more than 5 mg/L that is suitable for fish growth. The temperature of aquarium water was initially not controlled but when slow growth was observed then it was controlled with the help of aquarium water heater. The aquarium water temperature is controlled as 30°C.

3.3. Fish Growth Behavior in terms of SGR

The algal tank was also used for culturing tilapia. Tilapia fairly small in size group (20 g), were very susceptible to prevailing conditions in the tank (high ammonia concentration and low DO regime). The water characteristics of all acrylic tanks were tested at regular interval, to ascertain aquaculture criteria and examine fish growth. The total weight of five fishes for each aquarium was measured. The growth of fishes in terms of weight gain is shown in Fig. 2.

The fish growth was more in aquarium 3 that is 12 h night time aeration conditions and is followed by aquarium 2 that is with 12 h day time aeration. The growth of fish was very slow in aquarium 1 and 4 that aquarium with 24 h aeration and aquarium in absence of aeration respectively. Under controlled condition over 45 days period, the SGR values of aquarium 1, 2, 3 and 4 was measured as 0.8477, 0.9622, 1.3875 and 0.7305% body weight/day respectively. The result clearly shows that the highest SGR was obtained with aquarium 3 i.e., 12 h night time aeration condition.

Fig. 2 Mean Growth Behavior of fishes under different aeration conditions

Fig. 3 Growth behaviour of algae under different aeration conditions

3.4. Algal growth behavior in terms of algal biomass

The growth of algae was measured as dry cell weight and it is shown in Fig. 3. Microalgae cultivation generally requires inorganic nutrients and carbon dioxide in the presence of sunlight through photosynthesis. As microalgae require both organic and inorganic nutritional inputs for their survival, wastewater can be a potential source of these nutritional requirements and henceforth, micro-algae can help in bioremediation of UASB reactor treated wastewater (Kiran et al. 2014). The growth behaviour of algae was almost similar in all aquaria under different aeration conditions. The UASB-Algal-tilapia ponds offer marketable by-products as fish protein including algal biomass, which correspond to a cost recovery for sewage treatment. There was a 2 - 3 log scale pathogen removal after treatment in algal tank with MPN of the final effluent being less than 1000/100 mL, which is within the acceptable standards for surface irrigation. The generated permeate in UASB-Algal pond combined treatment system can be utilized for agro-irrigation, re-circulatory aquaculture system or disposed safely in inland water channels. The black water after treatment using UASB/Algal pond is being reused for gardening and landscaping. Nowadays power is very important issues for all purposes. Our study clearly shows that the algae reduced the inorganic nitrogen and results in good water quality for tilapia fish culture.

4. Conclusion

This study indicated the possibility for integration of UASB reactor and algal pond for sewage treatment along with tilapia fish culture. The results obtained from this experiment showed that the pH level of algal pond water was decreased as CO₂ concentration increased. The fish growth rates of aquarium of 24 h aeration and without aeration were lower in comparison with others. The growth was slightly higher in 12 h day time aeration and highest growth was obtained in 12 h

night time aeration condition. This shows that aeration affects the growth of fish. The tertiary treatment of wastewater is very essential part to remove organic waste present in wastewater. The tertiary treated effluent can be used for industrial processes, agriculture irrigation as well as ecosystem functions and services. The UASB-Algal-tilapia ponds offer marketable by-products as fish protein including algal biomass, which correspond to a cost recovery for sewage treatment. Now-a-days power is very important issues for all purposes. Our study clearly shows that the algae reduced the inorganic nitrogen and resulted in good water quality for tilapia fish culture. There was a 2 - 3 log scale pathogen removal after treatment in algal tank with MPN of the final effluent being less than 1000/100 mL, which is within acceptable standards for surface irrigation. The permeate generated in UASB-Algal pond combined process with 90 days of HRT of treatment can be utilized for agro-irrigation, re-circulatory aquaculture system or disposed safely in inland water channels. The black water after treatment using UASB/Algal pond is being reused for gardening and landscaping. Utilization of nutrients present in the treated sewage for the growth of microalgae species will not only control eutrophication but will also help in sustainable energy development. The findings of this study suggest that sewage can be directly used for mass cultivation of microalgae without requiring additional nutrient supplements. The effluent of the algal pond can be directly reused for surface irrigation of non-food crops. Operating cost is an important point of view as the algal biomass correspond to a cost recovery for sewage treatment by producing the biodiesel which can be further used as a fuel as 10 - 20% in addition with diesel.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by Agricultural and Food Engineering Department, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur. The authors are very thankful to Prof.

M.M.Ghangrekar, Civil Engineering Department, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur for his support. The authors are also thankful to Dr. Deepak Jadhav, Dr. Sumit Jain, Mr. Shaikat and to all staffs of Environmental Engineering Lab, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur for their direct and indirect support. The authors also thankful to all staffs of Aquacultural Engineering Workshop, Agricultural and Food Engineering Department, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur for their timely support.

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